

RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT OF OFFSHORE JACKET PLATFORMS UNDER PROGRESSIVE COLLAPSE USING PROBABILISTIC METHODS

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Abstract: *This study presents a probabilistic prediction of the progressive collapse of a four-legged, fixed-type offshore jacket platform (OJP) located in the central Gulf of Guinea (GOG). The platform, constructed in 1975, consists of a steel space frame with a 15.24 x 15.24 m helideck positioned 16.46 m above mean sea level (MSL) and a production deck at 7.92 m above MSL. Structural stiffness is improved with diagonal bracing in vertical and horizontal planes. The legs are horizontally braced at four levels and vertically X-braced. The platform is supported by four piles driven to a depth of 64 m and constructed using A36 steel, with specified mechanical properties (e.g., Young's modulus of 200 GPa, yield strength of 250 MPa). The study applied the Total Probability Theorem, reliability index, and reliability factor to estimate the platform's probability of progressive collapse (PPC). Series and parallel system reliability theories were applied, taking into account corrosion-induced member degradation. ANOVA was used for result validation. Bracing members were grouped (A–F) for analysis, with Group D exhibiting the highest PPC failure (0.6673) and lowest reliability (0.3327), while Group A had the lowest PPC failure (0.0840) and highest reliability (0.9160). Corrosion analysis showed jacket leg-1 had the highest thickness reduction (6.560%) and PPC failure (0.06560), whereas leg-4 had the lowest (2.360% and 0.0236, respectively) and the highest reliability (0.9764). Bracing reliability was 0.99945, jacket leg reliability was 0.8328, and total system reliability was 0.8323. With a dependability factor of 1.2020 lower than the load factor of safety of 1.25 and a reserve strength ratio (RSR) of*

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3.9868—well above the required minimum of 1.50—the platform is deemed structurally safe.

1. Introduction

To offer stability against the wind, waves, and current (WWC) loads of the sea environment, jacket platforms are fixed-type platforms that are fastened to the seabed using piles (Poonam et al., 2013). Exploration and exploitation of marine resources, particularly the extraction of natural gas and oil, are carried out on jacket platforms. The jacket serves as the platform's structural support. According to Yi et al. (2021), a jacket structure is a steel or steel-welded frame that takes the shape of a three-dimensional flat panel rack or plane truss, composed of a three-dimensional space truss structure. The jacket is fastened to the seafloor by a sequence of piles that are driven through or around its main legs. Unavoidable welding errors, residual loads, and the cyclic action of waves combined with the corrosive ocean environment cause fatigue fractures to form and enlarge at tube joints (Zhang et al., 2010). Offshore constructions may gradually collapse due to these potential risks and burdens, which include ship collisions, explosions, fires, falling objects, and extreme weather conditions.

The extension of local damage to the structurally intact portion, which ultimately leads to the failure of the entire building, is known as progressive collapse (Esfandiari & Urgessa, 2020; Fang et al., 2021). The loss of a primary

structural element, which is greatly impacted by corrosion, ship impact, and other uncertainties in predicting design environmental elements, such as variability in sea state parameters and inherent randomness in the wave process, including storm, wave height, wave period, current velocity, and other environmental forces on the structure, is how progressive collapse analysis of jacket platforms defines structural damage in the jacket structure (Alshaikh et al., 2020).

For example, platforms for jacket legs that use steel structures to offer a stable base at water depths below 200 meters are vulnerable to corrosion because of prolonged exposure to seawater immersion (Low, 2015; Ezanizam et al., 2019). For corrosion to occur, the metal must lose its electrons to oxygen and water, creating hydroxyl ions. These ions will subsequently combine with ferrous ions and undergo additional oxidation to create the frequently seen brownish rust and hydrated ferric oxide. In addition to harming the structure, further deterioration will make it easier for the platform to fail. On the other hand, a system's dependability is its capacity to complete its intended function within a given time frame. Specifically, the process of estimating and forecasting the likelihood of limit state violations at any point in the structure's life is governed by

structural reliability. Structural capacity and system load are the two main issues influencing the result in this reliability framework (Fayazi & Aghakouchak, 2015). According to Yang et al. (2017), system load is a random variable with a stochastic process over a specified time horizon. However, structural capacity is a function of strength and is susceptible to corrosion and fatigue uncertainty.

The economic and environmental effects of these uncertainties, causing progressive collapse of jacket platforms, should be considered during their design, in such a manner that local damage does not escalate into global failure. The probabilistic prediction approach is more important for jacket structures to determine the probability of failure (POF) (Qiang et al., 2020), the reliability, and to predict the progressive collapse of an offshore jacket structure because it is more accurate than the deterministic approach. This is because of the random nature of the environment and the uncertainties associated with the operation of offshore jacket structures. Specifically, it was discovered that 65% of Nigeria Water's offshore platforms were older than their initial design life, which was between 20 and 30 years (Igboanusi et al., 2022; Akobo et al., 2022).

The probabilistic approach is a technique that systematically computes all statistical data that are associated with uncertainties, such as wave height and wavelength, to predict the failure rate and progressive collapse of an offshore jacket structure (Kiakojoury et al., 2020; Abdulrahim &

Mohammad, 2017). To calculate the RSR and time to failure, the probabilistic model combines the load and ultimate strength models. The techniques make it possible to estimate how long an offshore structural platform will be able to sustain the loads despite its current state. Generally, the probabilistic approach is of three modes: frequency domain, probability domain and time domain. The frequency domain has wide application to marine structural responses because of its efficiency (Syed et al. 2021) and less assessment time compared with the time domain and provides a precise prediction with efficient outcome for real structures (Moan, 2018). However, actual values are inconsistent because the frequency domain does not account for nonlinearities in its computation. Although it uses linear wave theory, the probability domain includes techniques like the second and fourth statistical moments (SFSM), which are used to assess extreme response values and can conduct both short-term and long-term analysis. It performs exceptionally well in both low and high sea conditions. The time domain is employed to simplify nonlinear analysis connected with wave and wind, which the frequency and probability domains do not accommodate. The probabilistic approach exposes the inability of a structure to resist local failure and indicates the features of disproportional failure (Hossein et al., 2014; Rupam & Ghanekar, 2020; Osamah & Mahdy, 2021).

A key structural element that is greatly impacted by corrosion, ship impact, fatigue, stresses, or

uncertainties like these can be lost because of structural damage in jacket platform constructions. The main concern of this study is the inherent randomness in the wave process, which includes storm, wave height, wave period, current velocity, and other environmental forces on the structure; uncertainties in the prediction of the wave force on the jacket's structure; uncertainties in the structural model; and finally, uncertainties in the pile-soil interaction, which significantly reduces the jacket platform's ability to perform its designated functions and eventually causes the OJP to collapse (Low, 2015; Ezanizam et al., 2019; Adje & De Thales, 2021). Therefore, performing probabilistic prediction of the progressive collapse of a jacket platform is the motivation for this research to prevent global structural failure in the jacket platform due to corrosion of members.

To predict the progressive collapse of a jacket platform operating in the GOG, a probabilistic approach that evaluates geometric data, models the OJP's design while taking environmental factors into account, and uses the total probability theorem to determine the likelihood that the OJP will fail through progressive collapse is adopted. Additionally, the series and parallel reliability methods are used to analyze the OJP's reliability index and reliability factor. The collapse base shear and design base shear are introduced to estimate the OJP's RSR.

Offshore platforms must function under service settings, which include harsh operational and environmental circumstances with loads

produced by WWC. According to Lu et al. (2021), Jiang et al. (2015), Jiang & Chen (2012), a collapse may result from progressive collapse risks brought on by design flaws, construction bias, and unforeseen circumstances like loads (dead or permanent loads, live or operating loads, environmental loads, deformation loads, installation (construction) loads, and accidental loads) and corrosion. A structure's gradual collapse frequently begins with localized component failure (Kiakojoury et al., 2021; Kai et al., 2019). A collapse event could eventually result from such a failure spreading throughout the entire structure. Predicting the Jacket platform's gradual collapse to prevent failure is therefore a crucial aspect of structural design, construction, and operation.

Predicting the Jacket platform's progressive collapse to avoid structural failure has received a lot of attention, according to recent literature. Numerous authors have a professional interest in using probabilistic incremental wave analysis to evaluate offshore platforms under extreme waves, predict progressive collapse resistance of steel frame structures, and assess high-energy ship collisions with jacket legs (Long, 2016). Yang et al. (2017) conducted probabilistic progressive collapse analysis of steel frame structures against blast loads, whereas Gerasimidis and Sideri (2016) investigated a novel partial-distributed damage approach for progressive collapse analysis of steel frames. An assessment technique to forecast steel frame constructions' progressive collapse resistance

was introduced by Chen et al. (2016). However, these experiments only partially addressed the issue of anticipating the Jacket platform's progressive collapse to avoid structural failure.

While Fang et al. (2021) investigated progressive collapse safety evaluation of truss structures taking material plasticity into consideration, Hossein et al. (2014) investigated probability-based assessments of jacket-type offshore platforms using incremental wave analysis. According to them, in the event of unanticipated incidents, significant civic structures require a theoretical or numerical progressive collapse study. The dependability of a fixed OJP against earthquake collapse was investigated by Elsayeda et al. (2014). This study proposed a method for evaluating a fixed OJP's resilience to earthquake collapse. A nonlinear finite-element model that took into consideration the impact of pile-soil interaction was used to model the platform. A review of offshore structural reliability assessment using probabilistic procedures was conducted by Syed et al. in 2021. According to them, offshore structures need to be constructed to withstand enormous stress brought on by harsh environmental conditions as well as weariness. The preferred method for evaluating a range of natural waves based on the long-term probability distribution of wave heights and associated periods on the site is structural reliability analysis. For fixed offshore platforms, Ezanizam et al. (2019) conducted a structural reliability analysis. To design or reevaluate offshore platforms, the structural

reliability assessment (SRA) approach was created. It refers to an analytical method in which the necessary platform collapse strength and associated failure probabilities are used to derive the design and reassessment criteria.

A historical study of condition assessment methods for older fixed-type offshore installations that are contemplating decommissioning was conducted by Mohamed et al. (2020). The scientific articles published during the last few decades on the structural condition assessment of older fixed-type offshore platforms were included in their analysis. Igboanusi et al. (2022) reported a more comprehensive method for system reliability analysis of a jacket structure under both severe wave and fatigue conditions in their study on system reliability of fixed offshore structures under fatigue deterioration. The results made it clear that the stub thickness has a significant impact on fatigue deterioration. Seyed et al. (2022) evaluated the reinforced concrete frames' progressive collapse while taking the soil-structure interaction into account: a sensitivity index-based parametric analysis. They conducted a nonlinear static pushdown analysis using scenarios involving the removal of columns from the first story to examine the progressive collapse of the reinforced concrete (RC) frames. On the coast of Lebanon, Abdallab et al. (2021) conducted an analysis and design of a jacket offshore construction. According to them, oil and gas are found and extracted from the Earth's crust using enormous steel-framed constructions

called OJP. An offshore jacket structure's foundation failure and instability during installation were examined in a case study by Rupam and Ghanekar (2020). According to them, jacket-type fixed offshore platforms—which are typically erected in offshore regions with rather shallow water—are supported momentarily on mud mat or shallow foundations until piles firmly anchor them.

2.0 Materials and Methods

This study used the geometric data of the jacket platform and environmental loads, including

Table 1 Met Ocean Data for 100m Water Depth in the Gulf of Guinea (GOG)

Local wind, sea wave conditions	1 Year	100 Years	1 Year	100 Years
Maximum wave height (m)	3.36	3.99	2.35	2.79
Significant wave height (m)	1.89	2.41	1.32	1.69
Period (s)	7.1	7.4	7.14	7.14
Current (m/s)	0.15	0.15	0.26	0.26
Wind (m/s)	13.89	16.98	11.11	13.51
Direction (deg)	180 & 225		270	

2.1 Jacket Platform Design Geometric Data

The platform under study is a four-legged, fixed-type oil jacket platform located in the central Gulf of Guinea (GOG), as described by Elsayeda et al. (2014). Constructed in 1975, it is positioned at a water depth of 37.2 meters and consists of a steel space frame structure. The top includes a 15.24 x 15.24 m helideck located 16.46 m above mean sea level (MSL) and a production deck of the same size positioned at 7.92 m above MSL. Structural rigidity is enhanced by diagonal

wind and wave current (WWC) forces. Structural modelling and probabilistic analysis were carried out using the Structural In-place Analysis and Computer Modelling Software (SACS). After designing the jacket platform with CAD software, it was subjected to simulated environmental conditions. The progressive collapse of the structure was predicted using the JONSWAP wave spectrum to model local wind sea waves. Relevant wave statistics are shown in Table 1.

bracing in both vertical and horizontal planes. The jacket is horizontally braced at four levels and vertically X-braced with tubular components. The structure is supported by four piles driven to a depth of 64 meters. It was built using standard A36 steel, with properties including a Young's modulus of 200 GPa, yield strength of 250 MPa, ultimate tensile strength of 400 MPa, shear modulus of 79.3 GPa, Poisson's ratio of 0.30, and a density of 7800 kg/m³.

2.2 Method for Probabilistic Prediction of Jacket Platform Progressive Collapse

Due to the offshore structure's exposure to a random environment, a probabilistic approach was used to predict its progressive collapse. This method accounted for wave loads over the structure's lifespan and uncertainties in soil, materials, joint strength, and environmental factors when analysing the jacket platform's failure probability. Conditional failure likelihoods were calculated for different wave load levels using the total probability theorem to assess reliability. The platform's Reserve Strength Ratio (RSR) was evaluated using

applied loads and ultimate stress capacity. The jacket base was modelled in SACS with pile-structure interaction, where each leg is supported by a single pile extending 64 m beneath the mud line. The piles, with a 76.2 cm diameter and 3.17 cm wall thickness, connect the nonlinear foundation to the structure. The probabilistic method, which considers uncertainties like wave height and length, offers a more accurate prediction of collapse than deterministic methods (Alireza & Aliakbar, 2015). Figure 1 illustrates this approach.

Figure 1: Probabilistic Approach of Determining POF

The study used the Time Domain Method, a probabilistic approach, to analyze platform loading, structural response, resistance, and probability of failure (POF). The failure likelihood was determined by examining the relationship between applied loads and the platform's resistance

2.3 Parameters of Structural Reliability Analysis for Progressive Collapse

i. Probability of Failure (POF)

Combining all potential loading patterns, the likelihood of surpassing a limit state within a specified reference period is known as the POF. The POF, which measures the likelihood of failure occurring is expressed using the total probability theory according to equation (1) (Alireza & Aliakbar, 2015):

$$P_f = \sum_{all\ h} P[L - R > 0 | H_{max} = h]. P[H_{max} = h] \quad (1)$$

where,

$P[H_{max} = h]$ is the probability of a loading pattern that depends on wave height, h.

$P[L - R > 0 | H_{max} = h]$ is the likelihood that the loading impact will exceed the stated structural resistance, given $H_{max} = h$

The POF (P_f) is also given by equation (2):

$$P_f = 1 - \Phi\beta \quad (2)$$

where; Φ is a standard normal variate's cumulative distribution function (CDF) and, β is the reliability (safety) index

The CDF ϕ is obtained from the cumulative distribution table and the P_f depends on β .

ii. Reliability Model

The reliability 'R(t)' is obtained from the failure probability(P_f) using equation (3):

$$R(t) = 1 - P_f(t) \quad (3)$$

Equations (4) and (5) demonstrate how to express equation (3) in terms of the member's initial thickness and time-variant corrosion loss:

$$R(t) = 1 - \frac{t_p}{100} \quad (4)$$

$$R(t) = 1 - \frac{\Delta t}{T} \quad (5)$$

Where: T is the initial thickness of the member (cm), Δt is the thickness loss due to corrosion (mm), and t_p is the corrosion loss (%)

a. Series Reliability Model

Equation (6) can be used to express the system reliability estimation:

$$R_S(t) = R(p_A).R(p_B).R(p_C).R(p_D) \quad (6)$$

where components A, B, C, and D's reliability are denoted by R_A , R_B , R_C , and R_D . The likelihood that A, B, C, and D will fail is represented by P_A ,

P_B , P_C , and P_D . Equation (7) provides a Boolean logic representation of the system's success (S):

$$S = A \cap B \cap C \cap D \quad (7)$$

The system's Reliability or likelihood of success R_S is determined using equation (8):

$$R_S = R_A .R_B .R_C .R_D \quad (8)$$

It can be expressed as follows for components in series using equation (9):

$$R_S = R_1 . R_2 . R_3 . R_4 . - - - . R_n \quad (9)$$

The Series systems are characterized by the fact that the dependability of the system decreases with the number of components, and that the system's total reliability is determined by the least dependable component.

b. Parallel Reliability

There are two types of parallel systems: standby and active. All the components of an active parallel system are always in operation. Some of the parts of a standby parallel system will be ready to take over if other components fail (Elsayed et al., 2014).

Active parallel systems are those in which components A and B are always active. It is assumed that the system is always functioning under one of the following circumstances:

- (1) Both A and B are functioning.
- (2) Item A is functioning, and Item B has malfunctioned; or
- (3) Item B is functioning, and Item A has malfunctioned.

However, the system is said to have failed when both A and B failed.

Equation (10) is used to estimate the active parallel reliability system's reliability:

$$R_S = 1 - (R_A + R_B - R_A \cdot R_B) \quad (10)$$

where R_S represents, as usual, the system's reliability, and R_A and R_B represent the system's components A and B reliability, respectively.

In Boolean logic, the Stand-by Parallel failure (F) is expressed using Equation (11):

$$F = A \cdot B \quad (11)$$

The probability of the system failing is provided by either Equation (12) or Equation (13).

$$P_S = 1 - P_A \cdot P_B \quad (12)$$

$$R_S = 1 - \{(1 - R_A) \cdot (1 - R_B)\} \quad (13)$$

c. Jacket Group Bracing Reliability (Active Parallel)

Equation (14), which represents the bracing member arrangement in active parallel mode, is used to show the reliability estimation for group bracing "A" for jacket structures:

$$R_A = 1 - [(P_a + P_b + P_c + P_d - P_a \cdot P_b \cdot P_c \cdot P_d)] \quad (14)$$

where P_a , P_b , P_c , and P_d represent the failure probability of each bracing member or member thickness corrosion loss, and R_A represents the reliability of bracing group "A." Using the formula in Equation (14), the reliability of the additional bracing groups B, C, D, E, and F will also be estimated.

d. Complete Jacket Bracing Reliability (Stand by Parallel)

The reliability of the entire bracing group is parallel and is mathematically expressed as Equations (15) and (16). The reliability of the individual bracing groups A, B, C, D, E, and F is represented as follows: R_A , R_B , R_C , R_D , R_E , R_F .

$$R_{SG} = 1 - \{(1 - R_A) \cdot (1 - R_B) \cdot (1 - R_C) \cdot (1 - R_D) \cdot (1 - R_E) \cdot (1 - R_F)\} \quad (15)$$

$$R_{SG} = 1 - P_A \cdot P_B \cdot P_C \cdot P_D \cdot P_E \cdot P_F \quad (16)$$

Where the failure probabilities of each group bracing are P_A , P_B , P_C , P_D , P_E , and P_F .

e. Jacket Legs Reliability

The pile head for a fixed OJP is at the mudline. The dependability of the leg system is determined by the product of the individual leg reliability, as each jacket leg is essential for the platform's functioning correctly. Consequently, Equation (17) displays the system reliability R_{SL} for a four-legged jacket platform:

$$R_{SL} = R_1 \cdot R_2 \cdot R_3 \cdot R_4 \quad (17)$$

where the corresponding reliability for each of the four legs of each jacket platform is denoted by R_1 , R_2 , R_3 , and R_4 .

f. Jacket System Reliability

Along its length, the jacket platform structure is made up of braces and legs at various levels. Using network reduction strategies, the desired system reliability may be achieved. The combination of the jacket bracing and platform leg reliability determines the structural system reliability of a jacket structure resulting from corrosion loss, according to Equation (18).

$$R_{JS} = R_{SL} \cdot R_{SG} \quad (18)$$

iii. Reliability Factor

Since the structural parts of a newly installed jacket are free of corrosion, its reliability is 1 or 100%. To calculate the rate at which structural system reliability declines, a reliability factor (RF) is herein constructed between an intact and

corroded jacket. Equation (19) represents a mathematical representation of the RF:

$$RF = \frac{1}{R_{JS}} \quad (19)$$

iv. Reserve Strength Ratio (RSR) of the Platform

The RSR, which is defined as the ratio of the platform's ultimate capacity to the design loading (often 100-year wave loading), serves as the basis for the acceptance criteria for the ultimate strength level.

$$RSR = \frac{\text{Jacket Platform Ultimate Strength Capacity}}{\text{Design Strength Capacity}} \quad (20)$$

2.4. SACS Model Development for Jacket Structures

As earlier stated, SACS is a numerical tool for dynamic analysis, which is deployed in this study to predict progressive collapse analysis and determine the final strength of space frame structures.

2.4.1. Pushover and Free Vibration Analysis

The SACS tool was utilized to conduct a nonlinear progressive collapse analysis to determine the platform's ultimate load-bearing capacity. Two stages of loading were employed in

a nonlinear progressive collapse analysis. The initial phase comprises the dead weight and topside loads of the platform. The second phase entails incrementally augmenting the hazard loads until platform failure occurs. Concentrated stresses were applied at the master joints at the platform's center of gravity (COG). Due to the platform's asymmetry, the pushover study was conducted with loads applied in the global x-direction and subsequently in the global y-direction. The load is incrementally applied until the platform collapses. The lesser of the two values was identified as the platform's definitive base shear capacity. Figure 2 illustrates the preliminary findings of the platform static pushover study during the collapse phase. Numerous failures of the jacket's leg components and bracing, coupled with the bending failure of piles beneath the mud line, signified an impending platform collapse. The platform's dynamic characteristics, including the vibration mode shapes and natural frequencies, were derived from a free vibration study. The platform's torsional, surge, and sway modes are depicted by the initial three predominant mode shapes.

Figure 2: Static Pushover Analyses: x- and y-directions – platform at collapse step

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural Analysis Computer Software (SACS) was used to model the OJP. The findings of the nonlinear time history analysis (NLTHA) for dynamic response base shears are displayed in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Dynamic Reaction Base Shears: The Results of Nonlinear Time History Analysis

Table 2 shows the results of the nonlinear time history analysis.

Table 2: Summary of the Maximum Dynamic Reaction Base Shears Nonlinear Time History Analysis Results

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Random Variable	Value (kN)
Collapse base shear CBS – Platform Resistance	4000.000
Induced dynamic response base shear (DBS) for platform load, environmental load, wave load, current load, and wind load	1003.312

3.1 Failure Probability Analysis of the Jacket Platform

The failure probability of progressive collapse (PPC) for the Jacket Legs and Bracings was determined. The components of the bracings on the OJP structure were categorized into six (6)

groups, namely: Group A, B, C, D, E, and F. the corrosion loss and PPC failure for the jacket platform were analyzed. The results are captured in Figure 4. It shows that Group D bracing had the highest PPC failure of 0.6673 while Group A bracing had the least PPC failure of 0.084.

Figure 4: Jacket Bracing Probability of Progressive Collapse Failure

Figure 5 shows the failure probability of the jacket platform legs. It can be deduced that

Jacket Leg 1 had the highest PPC failure of 0.0656, and Jacket Leg 4 had the least PPC failure of 0.0236.

Figure 5: Jacket Legs Progressive Collapse Failure Probability

The relationship between failure probability and corrosion is seen in Figure 6. The results showed that the PPC failure for the jacket platform legs is

directly and linearly proportional to the corrosion loss of the jacket legs. This means that as the corrosion loss of the jacket legs increases the PPC failure for the jacket platform legs also increases.

Figure 6: Jacket Leg Corrosion Loss against Progressive Collapse Failure Probability

3.2 Reliability Analysis and Reliability Factor of the Jacket Platform
3.2.1 Reliability Analysis of the Jacket Platform

Structural reliability for the Jacket bracing groups is shown in Figure 7, the result shows that Group A bracing had the highest reliability of 0.916 while Group D bracing had the least reliability of 0.3327.

Figure 7: Jacket Bracing Structural Reliability

Also, the structural reliability of the Jacket platform legs is shown in Figure 8. The result

shows that leg 4 had the highest structural reliability of 0.9764 while leg 1 had the least structural reliability of 0.9344.

Figure 8: Jacket Legs Reliability (Series Systems)

Figure 9 demonstrates the connection between the jacket bracing's structural reliability and failure probability. From the result, the bracing's

structural reliability and failure probability are negatively correlated; that is, the more likely the progressive collapse failure, the less reliable the bracing is, and vice versa.

Figure 9: Jacket Bracing PPC Failure against Structural Reliability

Also, Figure 10 demonstrates the connection between the jacket legs' structural reliability and failure probability. Figure 10 reveals the results for the relationship between PPC failure and reliability of the jacket legs. The results showed

that the PPC failure is inversely proportional to the reliability meaning that as the PPC failure increases the reliability decreases. The results showed that a strong positive linear correlation exists between PPC failure and reliability of the jacket platform legs.

Figure 10: Jacket Leg Progressive Collapse Failure Probability against Reliability

From the results R_{SL} is obtained as 0.8328 and R_{SG} is 0.9994, Thus the reliability of the jacket platform R_{JS} is obtained as 0.8323 from Equation (18). This suggests that the structural

reliability of the jacket platform system is 0.83 (83%).

3.2.2 Reliability Factor

The structural reliability of the jacket platform structures is 0.83. Substituting values into Equation (19), the reliability factor, RF of the jacket platform is obtained as 1.2015.

Accordingly, Table 3 presents an estimate of the jacket reliability projection for 2024.

Table 3: System Reliability & Reliability Factor Estimation

S/N	Period	1975	2024
1	Duration	0 years	49 years
2	Support Legs (R_{SL})	1	0.8328
3	Jacket Bracing (R_{SG})	1	0.9994
4	Reliability (R_{JS})	$(1.0 \times 1.0) = 1.0$	$(0.9994 \times 0.8328) = 0.8323$
5	Reliability Factor (RF)	$(1.0/1.0) = 1.0$	$(1.0/0.8323) = 1.2015$

Because it displays jacket reliability reduction rates, the reliability factor is crucial for determining jacket safety over the working life cycle. Given that the load factor of safety is approximately 1.25, depending on the load being considered, the recommended value is between 1.0 and 1.25. Significantly, the jacket platform is safe because its reliability factor of 1.202 is lower than the load factor of safety of 1.25.

3.3 Reserve Strength Ratio (RSR) Analysis

The RSR gauges a structure's capacity to support loads higher than those established by the platform design. The platform can be kept operational over its planned service life by using this reserve strength. Prioritizing the inspection and repair plans and assessing the criticality of structural system components are two deductions for the analysis's findings. RSR is the ratio of the 100-year return period design base shear to the collapse base shear.

From the results in Table 2, we have, the CBS and DBS are obtained as 4000.000kN and

1003.312kN, respectively. Ultimate strength capacity is a measure of the Platform resistance: Collapse base shear CBS (kN)

Design strength capacity is the total of wave load, current load, wind load, platform load, environmental load, induced dynamic response base shear loading on the jacket for a 100-year return period, metocean loading, and design base shear DBS (kN). The RSR is 3.9868 derived from Equation (20). For a manned structure, the RSR minimum acceptance safety requirement is 1.50. Therefore, the jacket platform structure is safe because its RSR of 3.9868 is higher than the minimum accepted safety threshold of 1.50.

4.0 CONCLUSIONS

This work focused on the probabilistic prediction of progressive collapse for a jacket platform operating in the Gulf of Guinea (GOG). Using SACS software, the geometric data, design, and environmental factors affecting the offshore jacket platform (OJP) were analysed. The platform is a four-legged, fixed-type steel structure located in the central GOG. Corrosion-

induced thickness loss was used to estimate the structure's probability of progressive collapse (PPC). Bracing components were grouped into six categories (A–F). Group A had the lowest PPC failure (0.0840), while Group D had the highest (0.6673). Among the jacket legs, leg-1 showed the highest PPC failure (0.06560) and leg-4 the lowest (0.0236).

The research also evaluated the reliability factor and index of the structure. Group a bracings had the highest reliability (0.9160), and Group D the lowest (0.3327). Overall, bracing reliability was 0.9994. Jacket leg-4 had the highest reliability (0.9764), and leg-1 had the lowest (0.9344). The total reliability of the jacket legs was 0.8328, and the structural system reliability was 0.8327. With a reliability factor of 1.202 below the safety load factor of 1.25, the platform is deemed safe.

The Reserve Strength Ratio (RSR) of the platform was calculated as 3.9868, significantly above the minimum requirement of 1.50 for manned structures, confirming the platform's structural safety.

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